

ABILITY OF COMMUNICATING IN ENGLISH AS AN OPPORTUNITY TO KEEP UP WITH THE INNOVATIONS OF THE SPECIALIZATION.

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G'ijduvon tuman 1-son kasb-hunar maktabi umumta'lim fani o'qituvchisi
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Annotatsiya:

Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilida muloqot qila olish qobiliyati fan-texnika, mutaxassislik fanlari bo'yicha ilg'or yutuqlardan o'z vaqtida xabardor bo'la olish imkoniyati sifatida tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: muloqot, lug'at boyligi, innovatsiya.

Аннотация:

В данной статье умение общаться на английском языке анализируется как возможность вовремя быть информированным о передовых достижениях науки и техники, профильных предметах.

Ключевые слова: общение, словарный запас, инновации.

Annotation:

In this article, the ability to communicate in English is analyzed as an opportunity to be informed on time about advanced achievements in science and technology, specialized subjects.

Key words: communication, vocabulary, innovation.

Communication is commonly defined as the transmission of information. Its precise definition is disputed and there are disagreements about whether unintentional or failed transmissions are included and whether communication not only transmits meaning but also creates it. Models of communication are simplified overviews of its main components and their interactions. Many models include the idea that a source uses a coding system to express information in the form of a message.

English is a *lingua franca*, meaning it is a "bridge" language: When two people who speak different non-English languages meet, very often the common language they use to connect is English. This is why English is taught in many schools around the globe and why many international corporations are officially mandating English communication for employees in all global locations.

English is the common language of navigation, such as for air traffic controllers and airline pilots, and it is the most common language used on the worldwide web. It is one of the six official languages of the 193-member United Nations. It is also the language of scientific research, with some 96 percent of

science journals publishing in English. Some researchers report that learning English communication is as important to obtaining their PhD as their thesis.

English is spoken by about 2 billion people today. As a native language, English ranks third, but it is the number one language learned by speakers of other languages. In fact, more people use English communication as a second language than they do their own native language.

Innovation is the practical implementation of ideas that result in the introduction of new goods or services or improvement in offering goods or services. An early model included only three phases of innovation. According to Utterback (1971), these phases were: 1) idea generation, 2) problem solving, and 3) implementation.^[43] By the time one completed phase 2, one had an invention, but until one got it to the point of having an economic impact, one did not have an innovation. Diffusion was not considered a phase of innovation. Focus at this point in time was on manufacturing.

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